

Markers of decision points in three classical collaborative ranking tasks

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Abstract

In the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic, which led to a major shift from offline to online activities in the meeting realm, we collected the MEET corpus to systematically examine the effects of collocated (physical), remote (digital), and hybrid work meetings on collaborative decision-making (Esfandiari-Baiat & Edlund, 2024). The corpus contains purposeful meetings following Goffman (1961), with focused interaction maintaining a single focus of cognitive and visual attention through collaborative tasks. We recorded ten sessions of three meetings where participants completed a different classical ranking task in each meeting: the Camping game survival task (Hare, 1952), the NASA moon survival task (Hall & Watson, 1970), and the Desert survival task (Lafferty & Pond, 1974). Each session contains one collocated, one remote and one hybrid meeting with the same three participants.

Here, we describe the first steps towards annotation that will allow us to describe the ranking tasks as an incremental decision process and compare participant behaviours at similar steps along the process. We present the current state of the annotation alongside examples of speech and communicative behaviours occurring when participants *question*, *propose*, and *decide*.

References

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